

ON A CONJECTURE OF DEACONESCU

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Abstract

In 2000 Deaconescu raised a question about whether there exists a composite n for which $S_2(n) | (\phi(n) - 1)$, where $\phi(n)$ is Euler's function and $S_2(n)$ is Schemmel's totient function. In this paper we prove that any such n is odd, squarefree and has at least seven distinct prime factors. We also prove that any such n with exactly K distinct prime divisors is necessarily less than $2^{2^{K+1}}$.

1. Introduction

Let ϕ denote Euler's totient function. In 1932 Lehmer [7] conjectured that if $\phi(n) | (n - 1)$, then n has to be a prime number. A composite positive integer satisfying that divisibility is called a *Lehmer number* or number with the *Lehmer property*. Although this problem has not been settled so far, several partial results are known. Lehmer himself proved that if n has Lehmer property then n is odd, squarefree and has at least seven distinct prime factors. Cohen and Hagis [3], using computational methods, established that $\omega(n) \geq 14$, where $\omega(n)$ denotes the number of distinct prime divisors of n . Burcsi et al. [1] showed that if, additionally, $3 | n$, then $\omega(n) \geq 40 \cdot 10^6$ and $n > 10^{36 \cdot 10^7}$. On the other hand, Pomerance [9] proved that every Lehmer number n is less than K^{2^K} , where $K = \omega(n)$. Recently, Burek and Žmija [2] improved this upper bound to $2^{2^K} - 2^{2^{K-1}}$.

In 2000 Deaconescu [4] conjectured that for $n \geq 2$

$$S_2(n) | (\phi(n) - 1)$$

if and only if n is prime, where $S_2(n)$ is *Schemmel's totient function*, a multiplicative

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function defined by

$$S_2(p^\alpha) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } p = 2; \\ p^{\alpha-1}(p - 2) & \text{if } p > 2 \end{cases}$$

for all primes p and positive integers α .

This problem seems to be as challenging as Lehmer’s problem. Clearly, the conjecture states that for every $M \geq 1$, the set D_M of integers satisfying

$$MS_2(n) = \phi(n) - 1 \tag{1}$$

contains only prime numbers. We say that a composite integer n is a *Deaconescu number* (or has the *Deaconescu property*) if it satisfies (1).

In this short note we prove the following results.

Theorem 1. *If n is a Deaconescu number, then n is odd, squarefree and $\omega(n) \geq 7$.*

Inspired by the work of Burek and Žmija we will also get an upper bound for Deaconescu numbers.

Theorem 2. *If n has the Deaconescu property, then*

$$n < 2^{2^K+K} - 2^{2^{K-1}+K},$$

where $K = \omega(n)$.

Hernandez and Luca [6] proved that there are at most finitely many Lehmer numbers n such that $P(\phi(n)) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$, where $P(X) \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$ is any monic non-constant polynomial. We will prove the analogous result for Deaconescu numbers.

Theorem 3. *Let $P(X) \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$ be a monic non-constant polynomial. Then there are at most finitely many composite integers n such that $S_2(n) | (\phi(n) - 1)$ and $P(S_2(n)) \equiv 0 \pmod{\phi(n)}$.*

2. Preliminaries

In this section we shall collect some preliminary results. First, we give a group-theoretic interpretation of Schemmel’s totient function.

Definition 1. Let R be a commutative ring with identity and R^* be the multiplicative group of its units. A unit $u \in R$ is called *exceptional* if $1 - u \in R^*$.

Let R^{**} denote the set of all exceptional units in R . In particular if $R = \mathbb{Z}_n$, the ring of residue classes mod n , then by definition we have

$$\mathbb{Z}_n^{**} = \{a \in \mathbb{Z}_n : \gcd(a, n) = 1 \text{ and } \gcd(a - 1, n) = 1\}.$$

In 2010, Harrington and Jones [5] proved that

$$|\mathbb{Z}_n^{**}| = S_2(n).$$

Note that $\phi(n)$ is always even if $n > 2$. Thus M in (1) must be odd.

Lemma 1. *We have $n \in D_1$ if and only if $n = p$ for some prime p .*

Proof. If $n = p$, it is in D_1 . If $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} \dots p_r^{\alpha_r}$ ($r > 1$) with $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_r$ then $S_2(n) < \phi(n) - 1$ since $1 \in \mathbb{Z}_n^*$ and $p_1 + 1 \in \mathbb{Z}_n^*$ but $1 \notin \mathbb{Z}_n^{**}$ and $p_1 + 1 \notin \mathbb{Z}_n^{**}$. \square

From now on we assume that $M > 1$ and that n denotes an integer greater than 1 in D_M for some $M > 1$. Then we have

$$\frac{\phi(n)}{S_2(n)} > M \geq 3. \tag{2}$$

The next lemma due to Nielsen [8] plays an important role in the proof of the upper bound for numbers with the Deaconescu property.

Lemma 2. *Let $r, a, b \in \mathbb{N}$ and let x_1, \dots, x_r be integers such that $1 < x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_r$ and*

$$\prod_{j=1}^r \left(1 - \frac{1}{x_j}\right) \leq \frac{a}{b} < \prod_{j=1}^{r-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{x_j}\right). \tag{3}$$

Then

$$a \prod_{j=1}^r x_j \leq (a + 1)^{2^r} - (a + 1)^{2^{r-1}}. \tag{4}$$

3. Proofs

Proof of Theorem 1. By definition of $S_2(n)$ it is clear that n must be odd. If n is not squarefree then n has a prime factor p_i for which $p_i | \phi(n)$ and $p_i | S_2(n)$. In this case, if n is a Deaconescu number, then $p_i | 1$ which is impossible. Next, we show that $\omega(n) \neq 2$. When $n = p_1 p_2$, Equation (1) becomes

$$M(p_1 - 2)(p_2 - 2) = (p_1 - 1)(p_2 - 1) - 1 \text{ or } M - 1 = \frac{1}{p_1 - 2} + \frac{1}{p_2 - 2}.$$

Hence $0 < M - 1 \leq 1 + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{4}{3}$ and $M = 2$, which is impossible since M is odd. If $2 < \omega(n) \leq 6$, then $M = 3$ and $3 | n$. Indeed, if $n = p_1 p_2 \dots p_r$ with $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_r$, then (2) gives $M < \frac{\phi(n)}{S_2(n)} \leq \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{q_i - 1}{q_i - 2} = Q_r$, where $\{q_i\} = \{3, 5, 7, \dots\}$

denotes the sequence of all odd primes. Since $Q_r < 5$ for $2 < r \leq 6$, we get $M = 3$. If $2 < r \leq 6$ and $3 \nmid n$, then

$$\frac{\phi(n)}{S_2(n)} = \prod_{i=1}^r \frac{p_i - 1}{p_i - 2} \leq \prod_{i=1}^6 \frac{q_{i+1} - 1}{q_{i+1} - 2} < 3$$

contradicting (2). Hence $3|n$. But if $n = 3p_2 \dots p_r$ and $M = 3$, Equation (1) becomes

$$3(p_2 - 2) \dots (p_r - 2) = 2(p_2 - 1) \dots (p_r - 1) - 1.$$

Taking this equation modulo 3 we see that it has no solutions in primes. Hence $\omega(n) \geq 7$. □

Proof of Theorem 1.2. Let us write $n = p_1 \dots p_K$ where $p_1 < p_2 < \dots < p_K$. Then

$$\prod_{j=1}^K \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j - 1}\right) = \frac{S_2(n)}{\phi(n)} < \frac{S_2(n)}{\phi(n) - 1}.$$

Moreover,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\frac{S_2(n)}{\phi(n) - 1}}{\prod_{j=1}^{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j - 1}\right)} &= \frac{n \prod_{j=1}^K \left(1 - \frac{2}{p_j}\right)}{(\phi(n) - 1) \prod_{j=1}^{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j - 1}\right)} \\ &= \frac{n \prod_{j=1}^{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{2}{p_j}\right) \left(1 - \frac{2}{p_K}\right)}{(\phi(n) - 1) \prod_{j=1}^{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j - 1}\right)} = \frac{n \prod_{j=1}^{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j}\right) \left(1 - \frac{2}{p_K}\right)}{\phi(n) - 1} \\ &= \frac{\phi(n)}{\phi(n) - 1} \cdot \frac{\left(1 - \frac{2}{p_K}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{1}{p_K}\right)} < 1 \end{aligned}$$

since $\phi(n) > p_K - 1$. Thus

$$\prod_{j=1}^K \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j - 1}\right) < \frac{S_2(n)}{\phi(n) - 1} < \prod_{j=1}^{K-1} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_j - 1}\right).$$

Hence, the inequality (3) is satisfied for $x_j = p_j - 1$, $r = K$, $a = 1$, $b = \frac{\phi(n) - 1}{S_2(n)}$. From (4) we get

$$(p_1 - 1) \dots (p_K - 1) \leq 2^{2^K} - 2^{2^{K-1}}.$$

Since $p - 1 > \frac{p}{2}$ for all primes $p \geq 3$, we have

$$n = p_1 \cdots p_K < 2^{2^K+K} - 2^{2^{K-1}+K}.$$

□

Proof of Theorem 1.3. We follow closely an argument in [6]. Let

$$P(X) = X^d + a_1X^{d-1} + \dots + a_d \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$$

with $d \geq 1$. Suppose n is a Deaconescu number. It is known that there exists a positive constant c such that $S_2(n) \geq \frac{cn}{(\log \log 3n)^2}$ for all odd n (see [10]). Then

$$M \ll (\log \log n)^2. \tag{5}$$

Since $P(S_2(n)) \equiv 0 \pmod{\phi(n)}$ we have that $M^d P(S_2(n)) \equiv 0 \pmod{\phi(n)}$. Thus by (1), we get

$$(-1)^d + a_1M(-1)^{d-1} + \dots + a_dM^d \equiv 0 \pmod{\phi(n)}.$$

Let S denote the left hand side of the above congruence. Now we consider two case:

Case I. $S \neq 0$. Note that $\phi(n) \geq \sqrt{n}$ for all odd n . Then from the above congruence and (5), we have that

$$\sqrt{n} \leq \phi(n) \leq |S| < \left(1 + \sum_{j=1}^d |a_j|\right) M^d \ll (\log \log n)^{2d}$$

which implies $n \ll 1$, as we want.

Case II. $S = 0$. Then $(-1)^d + a_1M(-1)^{d-1} + \dots + a_dM^d = 0$ or

$$\left(-\frac{1}{M}\right)^d + a_1\left(-\frac{1}{M}\right)^{d-1} + \dots + a_d = 0$$

or $P\left(-\frac{1}{M}\right) = 0$. Thus we get that $-\frac{1}{M}$ is both an algebraic integer and a rational number which is impossible since $M \geq 3$. □

References

[1] P. Burcsi, S. Czirbusz and G. Farkas, Computational investigation of Lehmer’s totient problem, *Ann. Univ. Sci. Budapest. Sect. Comput.* **35** (2011), 43–49.
 [2] D. Burek and B. Žmija, A new upper bound for numbers with the Lehmer property and its application to repunit numbers, *Int. J. Number Theory* **15** (2019), no. 7, 1463–1468.

- [3] G. L. Cohen and P. Hagsis, On the number of prime factors of n if $\phi(n)|(n-1)$, *Nieuw. Arch. Wisk. (3)* **28** (1980), no. 2, 177–185.
- [4] M. Deaconescu, Adding units mod n , *Elem. Math.* **55** (2000), no. 3, 123–127.
- [5] J. Harrington and L. Jones, On the iteration of a function related to Euler’s ϕ function, *Integers* **10** (2010), #A42.
- [6] S. H. Hernandez and F. Luca, A note on Deaconescu’s result concerning Lehmer’s problem, *Integers* **8** (2008), #A12.
- [7] D. H. Lehmer, On Euler’s totient function, *Bull. Amer. Math. Soc.* **38** (1932), 745–751.
- [8] P. Nielsen, Odd perfect numbers, Diophantine equations, and upper bounds, *Math. Comp.* **84** (2015), 2549–2567.
- [9] C. Pomerance, On composite n for which $\phi(n)|n-1$, II, *Pacific J. Math.* **69** (1977), no. 2, 177–186.
- [10] L.-W. Yip, *On Carmichael Type Problems for the Schemmel Totients and Some Related Questions*, Thesis (Ph.D), University of Alberta (Canada), 1989.